

PARALLEL PAPER PRESENTATIONS

22 August 2023, Tuesday (5:45 PM – 7:00 PM)

**EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES OF STEM STUDENTS
DURING THE PANDEMIC: WHAT DID WE LEARN SO FAR?**

ABSTRACTS
Session 4-1

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The study aimed at describing the two – year online learning experiences of senior high school STEM students using various methods such as survey, open ended questions and interviews. Out of 402 senior high school students of Taguig Science High School under the STEM strand, 95 students from both grade 11 and 12 answered the online questionnaire and 5 students agreed to be interviewed. Results indicated that although students had high support from their family and high confidence on the use of educational technologies, most of them had mixed experiences on their lessons highlighting the adjustment of both students and teachers on force remote lesson delivery using online learning platforms. With this adjustment, teaching strategies employed are often ineffective overwhelming students, developing laboratory skills seems difficult to do, taking quizzes becomes nerve racking and pressuring especially on math related task, and digital divide became evident. Beyond these, however, students develop independent leaning, problem solving and critical thinking skills, resourcefulness, technological competence, flexibility, and control over their own learning. Acclimatization and adaptation played the key role in deciding the learning success on force remote learning and online classes have somehow provided the necessary and positive educational experiences required and needed by the students.